

***MAHMUD KASHGARI IS THE FIRST COMPARATIVE TYPOLOGIST IN THE
HISTORY OF LINGUISTICS***

**Matluba Kholmatovna Tursunova, Master Student, Level 1, Uzbekistan National
University, the faculty of foreign languages**

Scientific supervisor: professor Siddikova Iroda Abdukhuzurovna

Annotation. Mahmud al-Kashgari, a man of great erudition and talent for his time, created a unique, unparalleled dictionary, which has become one of the most valuable monuments of culture and history of the Turkic peoples. Modern Oriental studies, including Arabic studies and Turkology are unthinkable without this work. Turkologists consider this work to be the first comparative historical study that was more than seven centuries ahead of its time. In it they find a prototype of methodological principles that were established in science only in the 20th century. It is quite in demand in the contemporary reading environment. "Devonu lugatut turk" ("Dictionary of Turkish dialects") is Mahmud Koshgari's encyclopedic work on Turkic languages (1071-72). This work contains valuable information about Turkic clans and tribes that lived in Central Asia and Western China in the second half of the 11th century, their social status, language, history, geography, metrology and astronomy of this area.

Key words: scholar, work, invaluable, manuscript, unique, language, diverse

Annotatsiya. O'z davri uchun yuksak ilm va iste'dod sohibi Mahmud al-Qoshg'ariy turkiy xalqlar madaniyati va tarixining eng qimmatli yodgorliklaridan biriga aylangan noyob, tengi yo'q lug'at yaratdi. Zamonaviy sharqshunoslik, jumladan arabshunoslik va turkologiyani bu asarsiz tasavvur qilib bo'lmaydi. Turkologlar bu asarni o'z davridan yetti asrdan ko'proq ilgari bo'lgan ilk qiyosiy tarixiy tadqiqot, deb hisoblaydilar. Unda ular fanda faqat 20-asrda o'rnatilgan metodologik tamoyillarning prototipini topadilar. Bu zamonaviy o'qish muhitida juda talabga ega. "Девону луғотит-турк" ("Туркий сўзлар девони") — Махмуд Кошғарийнинг туркий тиллар хақидаги қомусий асари (1071—72). Бу асарда 11-asrning ning 2-ярмида Марказий Осиёда ва Ғарбий Хитой ҳудудида истиқомат қилган туркий уруғ ва қабилалар, уларнинг ижтимоий аҳволи, тили, тарихи, бу ҳудуднинг географияси, метрологияси ва астрономиясига оид қимматли маълумотлар ёзиб қолдирилган.

Kalit so'zlar: olim, asar, bebaho, qo'lyozma, noyob, til, rang-barang

In the history of the Turkic-speaking peoples, a special place is occupied by the work of the outstanding scholar-encyclopedist of the Middle Ages Mahmud Kashgari "Devonu lugatut turk" ("Dictionary of Turkic dialects"). This three-volume work " is in the full sense of the word a golden placer of the most curious and subtle observations on the phonetics, grammar and vocabulary of a number of Turkic peoples, the only

work of its kind that has brought to our time invaluable linguistic, ethnographic, folklore, geographical, historical information about the Khakan (Karakhanid) Turks, Turkmens, Oguz, Yagma, chigilyakh, Kyrgyz".

There is practically no information about the author, whose full name sounds like Mahmud ibn al-Husayn ibn Muhammad. It is known that the father of the scientist Hussein ibn Muhammad, originally from Barshan, moved to Kashgar, where Mahmud was born, who adopted nisba Kashgari, that is, he came from Kashgar. Mahmud Kashgari was born between 1029 and 1038. He began work on his creation in 1072 and finished in 1078. It is known from the work itself that in addition to "Devonu lugatut turk", Mahmud Kashgari created another work, "Kitab Javahir an-nahv fi lugat at-turk" ("The book of jewels of the syntax of the Turkic languages"). It has not been found yet.

All that is known about the life of Mahmud Kashgari is that he belonged to the highest circles of the Karakhanid nobility. The aristocratic origin allowed the scientist to receive, apparently in Kashgar - a major political and cultural center of that time, an excellent education. In addition to a number of Turkic languages, Mahmud Kashgari also knew Arabic and Persian. It is possible that he continued his education in Bukhara, Nishapur, Samarkand, Merv, Baghdad, where he not only visited, but also lived for a long time, collecting the materials necessary for his book. The author himself writes about it like this: "Although I come from Turks who speak the purest language, ... who by origin and their kind occupy the very first place...I have traveled a span of a span through all the villages, the steppes of the Turks. I have completely imprinted in my mind the lively and rhymed speech of the Turks, Turkmens, Oguz, Chigil, Yagma, Kyrgyz... And so, this book, after a long study and search, I wrote in the most elegant way, in the clearest language... I gave the name "Devanu lugatut turk" to this work.

The only copy of the work of Mahmud Kashgari was discovered in 1915 by the Turkish scholar and bibliophile Ali Emiri in a copy in the Istanbul market and is currently stored in the National Library in Istanbul. The copyist of the manuscript was Mohammed ibn Abu-Bakr ibn Abu-l-Fath as-Sawi.

The first publisher of "Divanu Lugati turk" was the Turkish scholar Rifat Bilge, who also carried out the first translation of the book into Turkish.

The "Devon" of Mahmud Kashgari was translated into Uzbek by Professor Salih Mutallibov and published in Tashkent in 1960-1963. "Devonu lugat turk" by Mahmud Kashgari is a unique edition, where, along with the usual vocabulary for a dictionary, there are numerous works of art, mainly folklore. The author himself writes about this as follows: "I compiled this book in this book in alphabetical order, decorating it with proverbs, sajs, sayings, verses, rajazzes and prose passages." Indeed, there are a lot of "decorations" in the book, and they are of the most diverse nature and content"

Judging by the literary sources used by Mahmud Kashgari, he was well aware of Turkic folklore and early Turkic medieval literature. If at the first stages of studying

the literary monument, some literary critics believed that Mahmud Kashgari used only works of oral folk poetry in his work, then with a careful study of the “Devon” it becomes obvious that this is not entirely true. Many of the passages given in the book belong to specific professional poets, although the author does not mention their names. This can be explained by the fact that there was no great practice of compiling such dictionaries at that time. The scientist, apparently, considered that the main part of his book is the linguistic part and did not take into account some nuances in the “literary” part of his “Devon”.

"The Dictionary of Turkic dialects" presents the main genres of Turkic folklore - ritual and lyrical songs, heroic epic, historical legends and legends. In addition, it contains information about anatomy, medicine, veterinary medicine, astronomy, geography, ethnography, etc. It consists of two parts. In the first part of his work, Mahmud Kashgari talks about the purpose of his book, provides information about tribes and clans speaking Turkic languages. In the second part of his work, a dictionary of Turkic dialects is given, catchphrases, samples of oral folk art are given.

"Devon" ("Dictionary") Mahmud Kashgari is the only monument of the Turkic dialectology of the early period, giving an idea of phonetic and morphological phenomena and the specifics of dialect forms. The Dictionary also contains texts of oral and poetic creativity of Turkic tribes and peoples of Central Asia, East Turkestan, the Volga region, and the Urals.

The work of Mahmud Kashgari, written using scientific methods of Arabic philology, is still of exceptional value for linguists, folklorists and literary critics.

References:

1. Mahmud-al-Kashgari. (2010). Code of Turkic words / Translation from Arabic by A.R. Rustamov, ed. I.V. Kormushina, notes I.V. Kormushina, E.A. Potseluevsky, A.R. Rustamov. Moscow: Eastern Literature. Vol. 1. (in Russ).
2. Mahpirov, V.U. (1997). Names of farancestors. Almaty: Institute of Oriental Studies, Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Kazakhstan. (in Russ).
3. National encyclopedia of Uzbekistan, Tashkent, 2000

